

STUDY OF IMIDAZOLINES BASED ON OLEIC ACID AS CORROSION INHIBITORS IN DIFFERENT ENVIRONMENTS

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For a long time now, based on the current environmental conditions, not only in our republic, but also in the worldwide it has been important to prepare conservation compounds with high protection against corrosion for the protection of metal equipment, and for this reason, the use of more composition-type reagents as corrosion inhibitors is preferred [1]. It is known that chemical additives are widely used in oil extraction and oil refining industries to protect equipment from corrosion, salt precipitation, and bactericides. It is for this reason that extensive research was conducted in this field in the CIS, especially in Azerbaijan, and industrially important inhibitors were created [2-3].

The aim of the presented work is to synthesize imidazolines in different mole ratios based on oleic acid and diethylenetriamine and hexamethylenediamine within the existing standards and add them to T-30 oil in different percentages to prepare a preservative liquid, and recommend for application after studying its physical and chemical properties in thermohumidity chamber, sea water and 0.001% H₂SO₄ environment.

Table 1.

№1	T-30 oil+sample1	5	Lasts 210 day	157	151
№2	T-30 oil+sample1	10	Lasts 210 day	Lasts 168 days	Lasts 168 day
№3	T-30 oil+sample II	5	Lasts 210 day	137	135
№4	T-30 oil+sample II	10	Lasts 210 day	145	141
№5	T-30 oil+sample III	5	Lasts 210 day	Lasts 210 day	Lasts 210 day
№6	T-30 oil+sample III	10	Lasts 210 day	Lasts 210 day	Lasts 210 day

Sample I: Synthesized Imidazoline in a 2:1 molar ratio based on oleic acid and diethylenetriamine

Sample II: Synthesized Imidazoline on the basis of oleic acid and hexamethylenediamine in a 2:1 molar ratio

Sample III: Synthesized Imidazoline on the basis of oleic acid and hexamethylenediamine in a 1:1 mol ratio

As it is clear from Table.1, in the individual addition of inhibitors to T-30

turbine oil, "steel-3" brand metal plates protection from corrosion in different environments ("Q-4" thermohumidity chamber, sea water and 0.001% H₂SO₄ environment) has not been shown to further increase in the corrosion effect.

References

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